

Grazed Fuelbreak Network in Andalusia RAPCA

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Goats in a fuelbreak area in the municipality of Iznalloz, Granada. Farm of Almudena López Galindo

The *Grazed Fuelbreak Network in Andalusia (RAPCA)* is an initiative developed by the *Andalusian Regional Government* that combines sustainable forest management with forest wildfire prevention strategies. Its main objective is to maintain and manage fuelbreak areas through the planned use of grazing, integrating livestock activity as an effective tool for landscape conservation and wildfire prevention.

The main objective of the *RAPCA* is wildfire prevention. By controlling vegetation, the risk of forest wildfires spreading is reduced. Another objective is the promotion of extensive livestock farming, supporting livestock farming as a means of sustainable rural development. It also influences environmental preservation, thus promoting biodiversity and ecological balance, preventing soil degradation and loss of natural habitats.

The network uses livestock for the maintenance of fuelbreak areas. Local shepherds and livestock producers are key actors in this model as they guide livestock to areas that need to be cleared naturally. Livestock species vary according to the type of vegetation, but goats stand out for their use of scrubland. Two case studies are presented: the first located on the southern slopes of *Sierra Nevada, Granada*, with a mixed sheep and goat flock owned by *Baltasar Pozo*; the second case corresponds to the fuelbreak area managed by a dairy goat herd of the *Murciano Granadina breed, in Sierra Arana, Granada, run by Almudena López*.

Livestock consume dense vegetation, which would otherwise be dangerous fuel. Grazing activity is carried out in a controlled manner and according to annual plans drawn up by forestry technicians, adapted to the characteristics of the terrain and the needs of the ecosystem, avoiding the intensive use of machinery and chemical products, thus reducing the negative environmental impact.

The *RAPCA* covers all *Andalusian* provinces and is integrated in the *Andalusian Forest WildFire Prevention Plan*. The fuelbreak areas managed by the network are usually located in strategic high-risk areas, especially in mountainous and forest environments where wildfires can have devastating effects, with approximately 14,000 hectares.

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